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1. Urazaliyeva Mavluda Yangiboyevna O‘ZBEK TILI AUDIOKORPUSI UCHUN PRAATNING FUNKSIONAL IMKONIYATLARI.....	5
2. Kuchkorov Khoshimjon Khasanzoda SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE UZBEK TRANSLATION OF THE WORK OF THE ALCHEMIST (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE TRANSLATION OF AKHMAD OTABOY).....	11
3. Ergashev Mirsaid Baxtiyor o‘g‘li SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT OF “LOVE-MUHABBAT” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.....	18
4. Eshboltayev Bobur Jo‘rayevich BOLALAR REKLAMA MATNLARINING PSIXOLINGVISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	23
5. Qurbonova E‘zoza HUQUQSHUNOSLIKKA DOIR TERMINLARNING SEMANTIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA ULARDA POLIFUNKSIONALLIK MASALASI.....	27
6. Abduxamidova Dilafruz Abduxabirovna TILNING TAFAKKURGA TAFAKKURNING TILGA TA‘SIRI.....	33
7. Usmonova Zarina Habibovna THE UNIQUE ASPECTS OF TRANSLATION IN ENGLISH SCIENCE FICTION.....	38
8. Valieva Noiba Abbasxonovna TIL VA JAMIYAT O‘RTASIDAGI UZVIY BOG‘LIQLIK XX ASR DOLZARB MASALASI SIFATIDA.....	43
9. Dilorom Ikramovna Hakimova “NAFS” KONSEPTINING LINGVOPRAGMATIK TAVSIFI VA TASNIFI.....	49
10. Xasanova Shaxzoda FE‘L FRAZEOLOGIZMLAR TARJIMASI.....	54
11. Ойбек Бектемирович Абдимўминов БМТ ИСЛОҲОТЛАРИ: СИЁСИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР, НАЗАРИЙ ЁНДАШУВЛАР ВА АМАЛИЙ ТАШАББУСЛАР.....	60
12. Хасанова Феруза Мирзабековна, Аҳмедов Нодирбек Алиевич ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА С КИТАЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.....	67
13. Усманова Салиха Юлдашевна, Мирзаева Шахло Ризаевна ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЦИЯ СОСТАВА И СТРОЕНИЯ РУССКОГО И УЗБЕКСКОГО СЛОВА ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА СТУДЕНТАМИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ГРУПП.....	74
14. Saidvaliyev Farrukh Saidakramovich, Subkhanova Aziza Khabibulla kizi ROLE OF ANTIDEPRESSANTS IN REDUCING THE FREQUENCY AND DURATION OF MIGRAIN HEADACHES.....	80
15. Ишанкулова Нилуфар Ташкентовна HEMIS ТИЛИ ФЕЪЛЛАРИНИНГ АКЦИОНАЛ ТАСНИФИ.....	85
16. Jabborova Dilafruz Ismatullo kizi USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES TO ENHANCE FINANCE STUDENTS’ WRITING COMPETENCE.....	91
17. Jo‘raqulova Mushtariy O‘ZBEK TILI PARALLEL KORPUSINING LINGVISTIK TA‘MINOTI.....	94
18. Maftuna Kamarova Umar qizi KOREYS TILI O‘QITUVCHILARINING O‘QISH KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA FLIPPED LEARNING TEXNOLOGIYASINING O‘RNI.....	99

19. Shoxida Ulugova Shoxruxovna LISONIY OBRAZ YARATISHDA DISKURSNING KOGNITIV-SEMANTIK VAZIFASI.....	104
20. Рашидова Камила Ахмаджонова ЗАРОЖДЕНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ДЕТСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ЯПОНИИ.....	109
21. Тошбекова Дилором Исмоиловна, Халимова Нодири Бахронкуловна РУССКАЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЯ И КУЛЬТУРНЫЙ КОНТЕКСТ: АНАЛИЗ УСТОЙЧИВЫХ ВЫРАЖЕНИЙ, ПОСЛОВИЦ И ПОГОВОРОК, ИХ ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЕ, РАЗВИТИЕ И РОЛЬ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ.....	116
22. Bakhronova Dilrabo Keldiyorovna, Umirova Dilnoza PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF PHRASES IN IAN MCEWAN’S NOVELS.....	120
23. Ikramova Kamola Shuhratovna THE IMPORTANCE OF MYTHOLOGIES, ARCHETYPES, AND MYTHIC UNITS IN THE CREATION OF A FEMALE IMAGE IN NOVELS “PRIDE AND PREJUDICE” BY JANE AUSTEN AND “O’TGAN KUNLAR” BY ABDULLAH QODIRIY.....	124
24. Buranova Madina Uktamovna, Ruziyeva Umida Abryukul kizi SEMANTIC AND PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF ANTHROPOCENTRIC IDIOMS IN CONTEMPORARY ENGLISH LITERATURE.....	129
25. Ergashova Baxora Sayfillo qizi ITALYAN XALQ ERTAKLARINING TARIXIY TARAQQIYOTI.....	136
26. Muhtarova Nigina THE USE OF AUTHENTIC VIDEO MATERIALS TO IMPROVE LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH COMMUNICATIVE TEACHING.....	141
27. Bayonkhanova Iroda Furkatovna KOREYS TILINI O’RGANISHDA MAQOLLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIKLARI.....	151
28. Ergashev Mirsaid Baxtiyor o’g’li SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT OF “LOVE-MUHABBAT” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.....	157
29. Рашидова Камила Ахмаджонова ЗАРОЖДЕНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ДЕТСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ЯПОНИИ.....	162
30. Ikromova Nigina Oybekovna THE EFFECT OF COGNITIVE LOAD ON THE TRANSLATOR: THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLINGUISTIC PROCESSES IN TEXT TRANSLATION.....	169
31. Эргашева Дилноза Тохировна АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПЕРЕВОДА.....	175
32. Nasiba Azizova THE CONCEPT OF LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI.....	180

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Kuchkorov Khoshimjon Khasanzoda,head lecturer at the Department of Uzbek Literary Studies,
Chirchik State Pedagogical University**SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE UZBEK TRANSLATION OF THE WORK OF THE
ALCHEMIST (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE TRANSLATION OF AKHMAD OTABOY)** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14799625>**ABSTRACT**

This article analyzes the process of translating the famous work of Paulo Coelho "The Alchemist" into Uzbek and the creative approach of Akhmad Otaboy to this translation. The main ideas of the work are about the internal struggle of a person, the search for achieving a dream and the purpose of life, the clarity of meanings and spiritual content in the translation of Akhmad Otaboy, the process of cultural adaptation. The translator's creative approach to work, adaptation to the aesthetic rules of the Uzbek language, as well as his attention to universal and spiritual values are studied.

Keywords: Alchemist, Paulo Coelho, Akhmad Otaboy, literary translation, content, creative approach, cultural adaptation, art of translation, cultural values, preservation of meanings.

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АЛХИМИКА (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПЕРЕВОДА АХМАДА ОТАБАЙ)****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье анализируется процесс перевода знаменитого произведения Пауло Коэльо «Алхимик» на узбекский язык и творческий подход Ахмеда Отабая к этому переводу. Направлены основные идеи произведения о внутренней борьбе человека, поисках достижения мечты и цели жизни, ясности смыслов и духовного содержания в переводе Ахмеда Отабая, процессе культурной адаптации. Изучены творческий подход переводчика к работе, адаптация к эстетическим правилам узбекского языка, а также его внимание к общечеловеческим и духовным ценностям.

Ключевые слова: Алхимик, Пауло Коэльо, Ахмед Отабой, художественный перевод, содержание, творческий подход, культурная адаптация, искусство перевода, культурные ценности, сохранение смыслов.

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**ALKIMYOGAR ASARINING O‘ZBEKCHA TARJIMASI XUSUSIDA BA‘ZI
MULOHAZALAR (AHMAD OTABOY TARJIMASI MISOLIDA)****ANNOTASIYA**

Ushbu maqolada Paulo Koeloning mashhur «Alkimyogar» asarining o‘zbek tiliga tarjima qilinish jarayoni va Ahmad Otaboyning bu tarjimadagi ijodiy yondashuvi tahlil qilinadi. Asarning insonning ichki kurashi, orzu va hayot maqsadiga erishish yo‘lidagi izlanishlari haqidagi asosiy g‘oyalari, Ahmad Otaboy tarjimasidagi ma'nolar va ruhiy mazmunning aniqligi, madaniy moslashtirish jarayonini yoritish maqsad qilingan. Tarjimonning asarga bo‘lgan ijodiy yondashuvi, o‘zbek tilining estetik qoidalariga moslashtirilishi, shuningdek, uning umuminsoniy va ma'naviy qadriyatlarga bo‘lgan e'tibori o‘rganiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Alkimyogar, Paulo Koelo, Ahmad Otaboy, badiiy tarjima, mazmun, ijodiy yondashuv, madaniy moslashtirish, tarjima san’ati, madaniy qadriyatlar, ma’nolar saqlanishi.

Paulo Coelho is one of the most famous science fiction writers of the 20th century, his work "The Alchemist" occupies an important place in world literature. The main theme of the work is about the realization of one's destiny, the internal struggle to achieve one's dreams and goals. This work attracted the attention of many readers with its spiritual and philosophical content and influenced their views on life. The process of translating Akhmad Otaboy's work "The Alchemist" into Uzbek is an important example of the art of literary translation. Otaboy's translation managed to adapt to the Uzbek language and culture, while remaining true to the most important values and purpose of the work. In the process of translating this work into Uzbek, it is very important to take into account the accuracy of writing, the preservation of meanings, the aesthetic and cultural aspects of the translated language. In this regard, the study of Ahmed Otaboy's creative approach to translating "The Alchemist", his success in conveying the spiritual content and language to the reader in a clear and effective form is the basis for highlighting important points in the field of literary criticism. and translation studies. This approach to translation is an important step in the development of the art of artistic translation in Uzbek literature and shows the significance of the concepts of spiritual and aesthetic values in it.

The novel "The Alchemist" attracts readers with its deep spiritual meaning and wise life lessons. The work was translated in 2003 by Ahmed Otaboy, who in his own style conveyed to the reader the content and spirit of the original work. The work deeply reflects the path of a person along the path of his dreams, faith in fate, listening to the heart and the process of finding himself.

"The Alchemist" is delivered to readers through Uzbek translation. Ahmed Otaboy's translation is one of such works, and its interpretation occupies an important place in Uzbek literature. Akhmad Otaboy paid special attention to the following aspects when translating the work "The Alchemist":

A) Preservation of the content and spirit of the work. The translator tried to convey the spiritual content and deep philosophical spirit of the original work to the Uzbek reader in an accessible and effective manner. In this process, it is important to translate specific expressions and spiritual concepts into Uzbek.

Paulo Coelho's work "The Alchemist" is written in a simple, fluent and at the same time deeply meaningful language. Akhmad Otaboy tried to preserve this style, since this book is written in such a way that it is easy for readers to understand. When translating, the experiences and ideas of the characters in the work are expressed in linguistic and cultural codes that are close to the Uzbek reader. For example, some Arabic and Islamic terms could be translated with a special emphasis.

B) Clarity of philosophical and spiritual concepts. The main themes of the work - such ideas as fate, dreams, will and movement towards goodness, it is important to understand in the process of translation and correctly reflect them. Akhmad Otaboy paid attention to the expression of figurative expressions and symbolic content in the original work with their alternatives in the Uzbek language. This gives readers the opportunity to feel the aesthetics of the original work. In order to make the

work accessible to the Uzbek reader and increase its spiritual value, the translator took into account national traditions, the charm of the language and mentality.

Akhmad Otaboy's translation differs from other translations for several reasons:

The translator paid special attention to adaptation to the language and culture of Uzbek students. This is manifested in the approximation of the symbolic meanings of the work, expressions or views of the heroes to the national concept. Preservation of the national spirit is one of the characteristics of his translation.

Thanks to the style of the translator, the work became fluent and simple in the Uzbek language, understandable to readers. This sets him apart from other translators, as some translations are written in too academic or harsh language.

A. Otaboy tried to clearly convey the philosophical content of the work. Perhaps he tried to express the symbolism of *The Alchemist* clearly and effectively. Other translations may not reflect this symbolism fully and accurately.

The translator brought the work closer to the reader by using alternative phrases and comparisons in the Uzbek language. For example, the translation is enriched with Islamic concepts or symbols associated with the local culture. He conveyed to Uzbek readers the main ideas of the work - faith in fate, the pursuit of dreams and the meaning of life, linking them to personal spiritual needs.

In some places, the translator used the method of free creative translation, that is, he tried to express it in a new, unique way, while preserving the meaning. Other translations focus on a more direct translation.

Akhmad Otaboy often used the following words and phrases in the translation process, since they are closely related to the theme and content of the work:

1. Spiritual and philosophical concepts: Destiny, Dream, Faith, Voice of the Heart, Wisdom, Path, Purity and Innocence.
2. Words expressing symbolic meanings: Alchemy, Jewel, Gold, Desert, Symbol, Sand, Kyzylgular.
3. Islamic and cultural phrases: Kaza and Qadr, God's will, Dua, Patience and gratitude.
4. Words describing the path of life: Journey, Search, Mastery, Science.
5. Phrases related to the characters and plot of the play: Shepherd, Destiny, Love, Guide.

Studying the linguapoetic features of the translator's translation of the work "*The Alchemist*" into Uzbek will help to understand how he recreated the content and style of the work in the Uzbek language. The central symbols in the work, such as "*Alchemist*", "*sands*", "*gold*", "*voice of the heart*", retained the essence of the ideas and used forms of expression familiar to the Uzbek reader. He found alternative words and phrases in the Uzbek language to clearly and effectively convey the symbolic meanings.

An attempt was made to make the language of the work attractive and effective for the Uzbek reader.

Description of characters and situations through poetic images. For example, the presentation of ideological phrases such as "*language of the soul*" or "*journey*" with a resonant and deep meaning. Idioms: Enrichment of such concepts as work and dreams, fate and will, with expressions close to folklore.

The translator took into account the lexical and semantic features inherent in the national culture and mentality in order to make the work more lively and familiar to Uzbek readers. For example, expressions related to traditions, etc.

To ensure the deep meaning of the work and its different interpretation for each reader, the translator retained the double meaning in the original text. For example, concepts such as fate or the language of the soul have both personal and universal meanings in different contexts.

The translation attempted to enhance the emotional and intellectual impact of the language in order to preserve the core ideas of Paulo Coelho and adapt them to the understanding of the philosophical audience:

- phrases that make you think for a long time.

- more effectively present spiritual concepts.

Akhmad Otaboy paid attention to translating the philosophical work in a form understandable to all readers, while maintaining fluency in the Uzbek language. To do this, he focused on the following: 1) Avoiding unnecessary and long phrases; 2) Simplicity of words and the use of simple vocabulary.

An important role was played by bringing the speech of the characters in the work closer to the Uzbek reader, enriching it with expressions suitable for national identity. The lexical features of Akhmad Otaboy's translation are important for a deeper understanding of his language and how it is adapted for Uzbek readers. Akhmad Otaboy selected words and expressions close to the national mentality and made the translation understandable and effective for the Uzbek reader. For example: spiritual concepts such as fate, gratitude, patience, travel. Words with mystical meaning, for example, dua, qazah-kadar, hikmat.

The vocabulary rich in expressions and comparisons that exists in Uzbek folklore is used. Akhmad Otaboy correctly understood the symbolic words and phrases in the works of Paulo Coelho and adapted them to the Uzbek language. For example, he used such concepts as "Alchemist", "language of the heart", "journey" and explained them close to the content of the work.

Philosophical vocabulary is important in translation. In accordance with the general content of the work, the following words are often found: Destiny, will, dream, voice of the heart, inspiration, good. These words help to preserve the deep spiritual content and course of the work.

Akhmad Otaboy paid attention to the translation of symbolic and abstract meanings in an understandable form. For example, such figurative expressions as "living language", "language of the sands", "guide" are simplified or enriched with alternatives specific to the Uzbek language during translation. Scientific and spiritual concepts in "The Alchemist" are presented by Ahmad Otaboy using Islamic terminology or vocabulary with historical content. For example: the use of words such as "gold", "manuscript", "wisdom". The translator translated freely in certain places to preserve the Uzbek language direction. For example, complex or broad sentences and phrases in the original are given in a meaning closer to the Uzbek reader.

The translator's stylistic features in the translation of Paulo Coelho's "The Alchemist" reveal his originality and creative approach to conveying the content of the work to the Uzbek reader.

The translator used the features of the language close to the Uzbek reader. He tried to adapt the work to the Uzbek mentality in order to facilitate understanding of the cultural context. For example, the studied cultural symbols (travel, fate, patience) are combined with alternative concepts in the Uzbek culture.

The symbolism and metaphors in the play are clear and effective. For example, such expressions as "language of the heart", "safar yoli" are filled with alternatives in the Uzbek language. The translator used rich wordplay and figurative speech patterns to make the language vivid and impressive.

The translation style is simple, focused on a clear transfer of content. Avoid overly complex syntax and heavy wording. The fluency of the text makes the translation accessible and understandable to a wide range of readers. In order to preserve the emotional impact of the work, an attempt was made to clearly reflect the author's thoughts in the Uzbek language. This is reflected in the speech, thoughts and emotions of the characters. For example, the dreams and feelings of the shepherd in the work are conveyed simply but effectively.

The translator made it understandable to the Uzbek reader without losing the deep philosophical essence of the original work. Orifon has preserved the symbolic and psychological aspects of spiritual reflections on life. Each character has a unique style, his speech helps to express individuality and emotions. For example, the characters of the work gained individuality thanks to the simple and sincere speech of the shepherd and the wise and profound thoughts of the alchemist.

Ahmed Otaboy tried to enhance the overall effect of the work by using the free translation method in some places instead of direct translation. For example, super-symbolic or foreign cultural elements in the work are adapted to the national culture. The main ideas of the work (fate, trust,

dream, language of the soul) are impressively translated, and special attention is paid to the main concepts.

The translator translated the work "The Alchemist" into the Uzbek language, the expression of national color served to bring the translated text closer to the Uzbek reader. National color is the main aspect reflecting the features of national culture, language and mentality in the translation process. Ahmed Otaboy presented it as follows:

1. The spiritual concepts in the work are enriched with Islamic meanings. For example, such expressions and concepts as gaza-kadar, dua, sabr, shukur are made close and understandable to the reader.

2. From a spiritual point of view, various concepts are adapted to the Islamic worldview, which increases the spiritual impact of the work.

3. Proverbs, comparisons and expressions characteristic of Uzbek folklore are used. For example, phrases such as "He who submits to fate reaches the heights" or "He who endures conquers the mountain" are suitable for the content of the work.

4. The speech of the characters is adapted to the national way of life. Uzbek national images are added to images of nature and the environment, such as the desert, sand, gold. For example, such concepts as travel or the path of fate are enriched with national symbols. Elements characteristic of the way of life and traditions are added, which makes the text more lively and meaningful for the reader.

Complex or typical expressions and metaphors of foreign cultures in the original have been adapted to the Uzbek language in a simple and understandable form. For example, instead of expressions typical of Western culture, the original uses expressions and symbols familiar to the Uzbek reader. The unique influence of the national language has been preserved. An attempt was made to reflect the national spirit with short and fluent expressions.

The speech and behavior of the characters are close to the Uzbek mentality. The sincerity of the shepherd, wise speech and desire for a dream resemble the image of the heroes of the Uzbek people.

National vocabulary was used to convey the philosophical content of the work in a form characteristic of Uzbek culture. For example, such symbolic concepts as the "language of the heart" are enriched with poetic and philosophical forms of expression in the Uzbek language. National images are added to the description of the symbolism and setting in the work. For example, scenes of Uzbek culture are reflected in the image of the desert or desert life. The translator's analysis of the mistakes and shortcomings of the translation of "The Alchemist" helps to identify some problems in the translation process. Like any translation, Ahmad Otaboy's work may have some shortcomings. They can be divided into the following main categories:

1. Free approach to the original text

In the process of free translation, the essence or spiritual content of the original text is insufficiently conveyed in places. For example, when simplifying complex symbolic or philosophical expressions in the original, the depth of the content is likely to be lost.

In some places, the translator made additions to the original text in the process of adaptation to the national culture. This affects the originality of the work.

2. Unclear interpretation of cultural elements

Some expressions and symbols typical of Western culture do not have figurative expression in the Uzbek language. For example, it is possible that the concept of "Personal Legend" has not received a deeper interpretation in a form acceptable to the Uzbek language.

3. Errors in language and style

It is possible that incorrect or simplified vocabulary was used in the translation without preserving the stylistic richness of the original work. There may be some errors in conveying the symbolic and philosophical meaning of the work. For example, the symbolic meanings of "The Alchemist" (creativity, self-awareness) are not fully reflected.

4. Excessive use of national coloring

In some places, in the process of national adaptation, there is a danger of deviating from the spirit of the original work. Excessive or incorrect use of expressions and elements characteristic of the national culture can change the overall effect of the work. Some parts of the work may lack the fluency necessary to hold the reader's attention. For example, simplification or too many negative thoughts can reduce the dynamics of the work. In some places, there are spelling mistakes or grammatical errors. This makes it difficult for the reader to understand the text.

In some places, the deep philosophical content of the work is lost in the process of simplification. For example, the depth of such concepts as the meaning of life, faith in dreams and personal myth are likely to be reduced.

Akhmad Otaboy paid special attention to the protection of his language culture in the process of translating the work "The Alchemist". This translation reflects a clear and correct transmission of meanings and the desire to preserve the content and spirit of the work.

When the translator translated Coelho's work, he tried to convey to the reader its spiritual and spiritual content. When translating this work, it is important to preserve the correct and existing meanings. In his works, Coelho depicts the internal struggle of a person, his desires and search for his personality. Akhmad Otaboy clearly and effectively translated such spiritual and moral content into the Uzbek language.

The translator paid attention to the artistic accuracy of the Uzbek language. He translated every phrase, every word in an accessible and effective way for Uzbek readers. In this work, the translator tried to clearly show the meaning of each word and the expressions corresponding to it. The psychological portrait of the characters in the work, their internal states, the content and description of the heart also impose a great responsibility on the translator. In Coelho's work, characters often foreshadow human suffering and internal problems. In Akhmad Otaboy's translation, taking this into account, the situations of the characters were adapted to the Uzbek language.

Akhmad Otaboy showed full respect for the spiritual values of the work. The work "The Alchemist" is an impressive teaching on the search for the true purpose of one's life and one's inspiration. Akhmad Otaboy managed to convey such a great moral and spiritual content in the Uzbek language.

The translator used translation methods adapted to the traditional values, language and interaction of the Uzbek people, taking into account the cultural context. This, in turn, helped to make the work more accessible and understandable for Uzbek readers.

Akhmad Otaboy's creative and spiritual approach to the translation of "The Alchemist" has made a great contribution to the culture of translation in Uzbek literature. His work contributes to the creation of quality works that are very compatible with our language and culture, dedicated to Islamic and universal values.

In conclusion, we can say that Akhmad Otaboy's translation is distinguished by its compatibility with the national mentality, simplicity of language and deep spiritual content. The translator's translation activity is probably a creative endeavor that sought to preserve its original philosophical essence and at the same time deeply adapt the ideological and aesthetic aspects of the work to the Uzbek language. Linguistic aspects embody national culture, emotional impact and spiritual depth.

The translation of "The Alchemist" is lexically adapted to the national mentality, in a free and understandable language, preserving the philosophical and spiritual content. His work is distinguished by the correct choice of symbolic, cultural and poetic vocabulary.

The translator's translation style is in harmony with the national culture, simple, fluent and philosophical. Its stylistic features serve to bring it closer to the mentality and understanding of the language of Uzbek readers, without losing the deep meaning of the work.

The translation of Akhmad Otaboy is a creative approach aimed at preserving the national flavor. His translation, combined with the national culture and language, fully conveys to the reader not only the main idea of the work, but also its emotional and spiritual impact. Although the translator's translation is generally successful, in places it may fail to convey the philosophical depth, symbolic essence or stylistic aspects of the original work. These shortcomings are probably due

mainly to cultural adaptation, methodological simplification or free translation. It is possible that Ahmad Otaboy's translation contains Russian words, but the context and number of their use depend on the overall content of the work and the style of translation.

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